

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl no	R	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}
1	CH ₃	197d	76	C ₇ H ₈ N ₆ S	3 240, 3 110 (NH), 1 600 (C=N)
2	C ₂ H ₅	192	82	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₆ S	3 240, 3 140, 1 610
3	C ₆ H ₅	218	84	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₆ S	3 362, 1 610
4	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	152d	77	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ S	3 420, 1 620
5	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	202	76	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₆ S	3 300, 1 610
6	4'-Pyridyl	232	77	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₇ S	3 280, 1 630
7	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₃	188	81	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ OS	3 310, 1 610, 1 230, 1 025 (Ar-O-R)
8	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	220	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ OS	3 310, 1 590, 1 220, 1 202, 1 030
9	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	230	78	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₆ OS	3 310, 1 605, 1 228, 1 020

*C, H, N and S analyses were found to be satisfactory for all compounds

4-triazoles¹ (1) with 4-bromo-3-methyl-pyrazol-5-one (2) following the reported procedure. The structures of the products were based on elemental analyses and ir spectral data (Table 1).

The ir spectra (KBr) of 3 did not show bands due to carbonyl and mercapto groups, thus confirming the cyclic structure 3. Strong intensity absorption bands at 1 070–1 000 cm^{-1} due to aromatic ether linkage (Ph-O-R) at position-3 were observed for 3 (R=aryloxymethyl), and NH vibrations were observed at 3 600–3 200 cm^{-1} .

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tetra-bromo-1,4-benzoquinone using Diheteroalicyclic Compounds as Reagents

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BROMOSUBSTITUTED 1,4-benzoquinones are reported to be stronger acids as compared to chloro-substituted quinones¹. 2,3,5,6-Tetrabromo-1,4-benzoquinone (bromanil) is an oxidant² and used as an analytical reagent³. Some coulometric titrations^{4,5} and spectrophotometric methods^{6,7} are suggested for chloranil. However, no attempt has, so far been made for the determination of bromanil, except the one method reported by us earlier⁶.

Bromanil is a good π -acceptor and it is known to form electron donor-acceptor complexes with heteroalicyclic compounds⁸. Based on this, three diheteroalicyclic compounds, morpholine, thiomorpholine and piperazine were examined as reagents for the determination of bromanil by spectrophotometric method. We present here the results of such study.

Experimental

Bromanil was prepared and purified as reported earlier⁸. Morpholine and thiomorpholine (both Fluka) were purified by distillation on potassium hydroxide, while piperazine (EGA) was recrystallised from cyclohexane.

A Carl-Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorbance.

Stock solutions of bromanil (5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and the reagents (each about 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) were prepared in chloroform. An aliquot (0.3–1.5 ml) of

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quinone was mixed with the reagent (5 ml) and made upto 10 ml. The absorbance of the solutions was measured after 25 min against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Morpholine, thiomorpholine and piperazine are known as twin site n-donors. The electron donor-acceptor interaction of bromanil with these compounds leads to the formation of charge transfer complexes⁸. The complexes formed are stable in the presence of excess bromanil, but transform to yellow coloured disubstitution products in excess reagents.

para-Benzoquinones generally cause a strong intense π - π^* transition in the ultraviolet region⁹. By replacing the hydrogen and halogen atoms of quinone with electron-donating amino groups, the quinone exhibits a large bathochromic shift. The molar absorptivity values are slightly diminished upon substitution. However, the absorption maxima are markedly red-shifted, from ultraviolet to visible region.

The substitution product of bromanil with morpholine has an absorption maximum at 441 nm ($\log \epsilon = 4.01$) and the products with thiomorpholine and piperazine at 446 (4.03) and 449 nm (4.05), respectively. The unsubstituted quinone has the absorption maximum at 313 nm ($\epsilon = 4.25$). By following the visible absorption of the substitution products, the spectrometric determination of bromanil is made very simple.

The present method of estimation is based on the simple conversion of 2,3,5,6-tetrabromo-1,4-benzoquinone to 2,5-di-R-3,6-dibromo-1,4-benzoquinone, where R is the reagent. The proposed method tolerates a wide variation in the concentration of the reagent. Solution containing 5×10^{-4} to 8×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ of the reagent is found to be useful for the determination. However, a lower concentration of the reagent (1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) is favourable for the rapid conversion of tetrabromoquinone to diamino-dibromoquinone.

The time required to attain maximum absorbance of the final products with 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ was about 23 min. The absorbance values so obtained remained unchanged even after a day, provided the solutions were protected from light and kept in stoppered bottles.

Beer's law range and Sandell's sensitivity values are listed in Table 1. The data indicate that the proposed method is sensitive to microgram quantities of bromanil precise and accurate upto 1%.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR DETERMINATION OF BROMANIL

Reagent	Morpho- line	Thio- morpholine	Piperazine
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g mol}^{-1}$)	4-28	4-28	4-22
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.0409	0.0392	0.0374

Parent benzoquinone and chloranil are found to interfere at all concentrations. However, methyl-, 2,6-dimethyl-, 2-methyl-5-isopropyl- and tetramethyl-1,4-benzoquinones and benzoquinone-4-chlorimide do not interfere upto 25-fold excess.

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